

Key Insights on Leadership and Futures Studies

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Abstract: This paper identifies the top ten articles on leadership and futures studies published by the Nuts About Leadership (NAL) Journal in 2024. It serves as a retrospective analysis highlighting articles that significantly contribute to readers' understanding of leadership and foresight topics while advancing research in these fields. The selection of articles is based on the editorial board's recommendations and feedback from readers collected through an online poll. The articles are recapped and analyzed according to their contributions to the core components of leadership and foresight knowledge, including but not limited to transformational leadership, corporate foresight capabilities, and the dynamics of organizational culture. Each article provides unique insights into how leadership practices can be effectively aligned with strategic foresight to navigate complex challenges in various sectors.

Keywords: foresight; futures studies; leadership; leadership research; leadership studies

1. Introduction

NAL is a peer-reviewed journal focused on leadership and futures studies. It aims to explore various dimensions of leadership and its impact on future developments. The journal published 24 articles, including this paper across four issues in 2024, focusing on cognitive diversity and team effectiveness while showcasing contemporary research and discussions in the field.

Founded by Alireza Hejazi, the journal is committed to advancing the study of leadership through scholarly articles and discussions. It covers a variety of topics related to leadership and foresight. Leadership theories, cognitive diversity, team dynamics, future studies, organizational culture, ethical leadership, and leadership development shape the scope of the journal. These topics reflect the journal's commitment to advancing the discourse on leadership in various contexts.

In the evolving landscape of leadership studies, the intersection of theory and practice plays a pivotal role in shaping effective leadership strategies. This culminating paper aims to synthesize key insights from ten influential articles published in our journal that focus on leadership and futures studies. Each selected article contributes to a broader understanding of how leadership paradigms are adapting to contemporary challenges, including future-oriented rivalries, market volatility, and organizational effectiveness.

The articles reviewed span a range of topics, from inspecting the generalizability of leadership research findings to the development of a matrix by which the impact of leadership may be measured. For instance, one study identifies crucial factors that impact the effectiveness of U.S. global leadership.¹ Another article envisions the future of leadership in the age of generative artificial intelligence (AI).²

By recapping these seminal works, this paper honors the contributions of past research and sets the stage for future inquiries into leadership. The synthesis presented herein will serve as a reference for scholars and practitioners alike. It offers an overview of the current state of knowledge and identifies potential avenues for further exploration. As we face an increasingly complex world, understanding these foundational concepts will be crucial for developing effective leadership capacity that is responsive to both

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organizational needs and societal expectations. For instance, some articles explore the role of cognitive biases and diversities in leaders' leadership and foresight, while others examine the impact of decision-making styles and person-job fitness on the functionality of leaders and professional futurists.

By synthesizing these pivotal works, this paper provides readers with a report on the current landscape of leadership and futures studies. It reminds the value of interdisciplinary approaches in addressing contemporary issues. This analysis recognizes the contributions of these articles and shapes a foundation for future research endeavors that seek to further explore the interplay between leadership and foresight in an increasingly dynamic world.

2. Developing a New Perspective on Leadership

For decades, the generalizability of leadership research findings has been of concern. This concern is shaped mainly by the complexities of human behavior in diverse organizational contexts. The results of a study published by NAL suggest that to improve the generalizability of research findings in the domain of leadership scholars should employ a mixed methods research approach, which integrates qualitative and quantitative methodologies and amplifies the extent to which findings can be applied beyond their original context.³ Scholars should be also cautious about the illusion of generalizability that can arise from relying solely on large-team science projects. Instead, they should consider how their methods encompass or exclude underrepresented populations. Besides, a generative causal modeling framework can be utilized to determine which inferences can be made. It seems that expanding eligibility criteria alone may not suffice to improve generalizability. Therefore, scholars should consider targeting multiple subpopulations to generate relevant outcomes that apply to a wider population.

Beyond topics like the generalizability of leadership research findings, the utilization of generative AI technology across diverse domains, including organizational leadership has been of researchers' interest due to its multiple impacts. Comprising visioning and strategy formulation, communication, decision-making, team establishment, and change control are among those effects. The outcomes of the research suggested that generative AI technology could improve the strategic planning capabilities of enterprises.⁴ Nonetheless, the incorporation of AI-driven services in organizational leadership practices also poses challenges, like the necessity to tackle information scarcity and bolster internal reputation perceptions among staff members. Acknowledging these challenges, organizational leaders will need to take a balanced approach to leveraging generative AI technology within their enterprises.

Thinking about the AI and humans' interactions with it may lead researchers to refocus on humans and their mental abilities and limitations. A study examined the nexus of cognitive diversity, transformational leadership, and team effectiveness in organizational contexts. It found that transformational leadership and team effectiveness are significantly positively correlated.⁵ If organizations want to become more effective, they should think about putting procedures in place for locating, hiring, and training people who exhibit transformational leadership qualities for positions of leadership within their organizations. It appears that transformational leadership and team effectiveness are meaningfully correlated. According to the study's findings, there seems to be no significant correlation between cognitive diversity and team effectiveness moderated by transformational leadership.

Similarly, another study examined the link between decision-making styles and bias manifestations. The results proposed that organizational leaders who demonstrate rational decision-making styles are less susceptible to cognitive biases, while those who rely on intuition in their decision-making processes are more prone to cognitive biases.⁶ The theoretical implications of this study add to the body of knowledge on decision-making theory. Risk management, strategy planning, and ethical decision-making practices may be also impacted by the practical ramifications of leaders' cognitive biases. By applying the findings of the study, organizational leaders may increase the effectiveness of their decision-making, their ability to withstand cognitive biases, and their use of ethical decision-making techniques.

Finally, scholars have developed an assessment tool to evaluate leadership effectiveness through the perceptions of subordinates. By focusing on two dimensions, the Leadership Impact Matrix (LIM) enhances leaders' awareness of their leadership practices

and helps them improve their team performance, and develop a culture of continuous growth through a guided evaluation.⁷ The primary dimension of LIM assesses how leaders guide and empower their teams. The secondary dimension evaluates leaders' motivational influence on team dynamics and individual behaviors. LIM's reliability and validity are established through relevant tests. This assessment tool operates by a scoring system that facilitates targeted feedback for individual development and organizational assessment. The instrument can be useful for organizational leaders who seek insights to better align their leadership strategies with the needs of their teams.

3. Rethinking Futures Studies

Various methods may be applied to envision different futures and one of them is scenario building. The scenario method has been used widely by many managers and leaders for strategic planning. The method involves exploring potential future situations and development paths over a medium-term timeframe. However, it is exposed to potential biases, especially if it is utilized through techniques such as the 2x2 matrix method. A new study found that confirmation bias, availability bias, and overconfidence bias associated with the method could have an impact on the scenarios developed.⁸ While this phenomenon can be partly explained by the researchers' way of using the 2x2 matrix method, it is intrinsic to the method, making it susceptible to cognitive biases. The study adds to the assessment of futures studies by suggesting tactics and recommendations that could improve the use of the method, especially if foresight practitioners agree with the ideas of challenging their presumptions and scenario building and employing a wider range of perspectives beyond their own.

The growing need for rethinking futures studies embraces other methods and aspects of the field. For example, maturity assessment models provide a structured approach to measure and enhance foresight practices. However, rethinking the concept of maturity in corporate foresight seems necessary for two reasons. Firstly, traditional maturity assessments often follow a linear progression model, which may not adequately address the complexities and unpredictabilities of contemporary business environments. Secondly, the assessment campaigns and models often cover a limited scope of industries, sectors, or companies, which may not provide a comprehensive view of maturity levels. A study explored the limitations of maturity assessment in corporate foresight and suggested strategies for enhancing organizational agility and resilience.⁹ It proposed a framework for assessing maturity in corporate foresight that considers organizations' dynamic capabilities, and micro- and macro-environments, and recommends agile foresight practices, cross-disciplinary collaboration, and continuous learning and improvement.

Such frameworks may raise foundational questions like this: What value is created from corporate foresight as a source of a firm's future competitive advantage? To address the question, researchers developed a measure that aggregates various data points to assess corporate foresight. The Corporate Foresight Index (CFI) provides a systematic approach for evaluating foresight capabilities at the corporate level.¹⁰ It is a measure that assesses corporate foresight capabilities quantifiably. The CFI evaluates corporate foresight by assessing nine strategic achievements that may be gained through foresight. This assessment is conducted through a scoring system using a 36-item questionnaire. It enables practitioners and auditors to measure corporate foresight capabilities using a five-point Likert scale. The scoring results help identify the corporation's orientation toward one of the three modes of preparedness for the future. Corporations may utilize the recommendations that the CFI suggests according to their score ranges to enhance their foresight capabilities. The study contributes to the field by providing a measurement tool that facilitates evaluating corporate foresight capabilities.

Evaluating foresight capabilities can go well beyond the corporate level and also embrace the personal level. In recent years, some professional futurists have been thinking of ways by which they may be able to evaluate their qualifications and suitability for different roles they desire to play. Inspired by that sense of curiosity, a group of researchers developed a self-assessment tool that can be used to evaluate the qualifications and suitability of futurists for various roles. The Futurist-Job Fit Measure (FJFM) categorizes futurists into six distinct types and provides valuable insights into areas for professional development and alignment with desired roles.¹¹ The FJFM enhances futurists' self-awareness through 45 indicators. It also serves as a strategic tool for organizations seeking to optimize their workforce in strategic foresight. The FJFM appears to be a useful instrument for assessing person-job fit among futurists.

The evaluation of foresight may extend to more aspects of the field, including theories, practices, and methods. Foresight practitioners have been thinking of when, why, and how to implement foresight methods effectively. Understanding the need for criteria by which users may select and apply those methods correctly, researchers have developed a tool that assists users in this regard. Futures Methods Compass (FMC) provides a structured approach to determining which foresight methods should be utilized.¹² It guides users through the complexities of futures studies and facilitates the informed choice of a diverse array of research methods. It helps foresight practitioners use relevant methods individually or in combination according to their research variables and objectives. The tool covers various methods such as backcasting, cross-impact analysis, environmental scanning, the futures wheel, the Delphi method, scenario planning, and trend analysis. FMC is a diagnostic instrument that leads users through intricate methodological decisions. The paper published through NAL demonstrates the tool's applicability across different contexts.

4. Conclusion

This review paper has synthesized key findings from a selection of articles that explore the evolving landscape of leadership in the context of contemporary challenges and innovations. The articles collectively highlight the transformative impact of new technologies like generative AI on leadership practices, emphasizing the need for leaders to adapt their strategies to leverage technological advancements effectively. The exploration of cognitive diversity and its relationship with transformational leadership underscores the value of inclusive practices that enable team effectiveness in organizational settings.

Furthermore, the analysis of decision-making styles and cognitive biases reveals critical insights into how leaders can enhance their strategic choices by recognizing and mitigating inherent biases. The LIM and the CFI provide valuable frameworks for assessing leadership effectiveness and foresight capabilities, respectively, while the FJFM and FMC offer practical tools for aligning leadership roles with future-focused methodologies.

The findings from these articles remind leaders of the necessity to cultivate a forward-thinking mindset, embrace cognitive diversity, and apply strategic foresight in their decision-making processes. This body of work advances our understanding of leadership dynamics and sets a foundation for future research exploring the interplay between leadership and foresight. By shaping a capacity for adaptability and innovation, leaders can better position themselves and their organizations to face new challenges.

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